

IPBES TCA Chapter 4. Review of literature on institutional misfits and inadequate policies / IPBES transformative change assessment

Process 2 on institutional fit and spatial fit - Screening rules

- **Screening Step #1: Abstract reading and screening**
 - **exclude (i.e., mark as red) if:**
 - Paper address issues of biodiversity/ecosystems but it is not about institutions/governance problems/barriers/unfitness
 - Paper conceptualizes drivers or patterns/types of institutional misfits but does not relate with biodiversity/nature/environmental issues
 - **include (green) only if:**
 - Paper addresses issues of biodiversity/ecosystems AND discuss institutions/governance problems/barriers/unfitness
 - Paper conceptualizes drivers or patterns/types of institutional misfits RELATED TO biodiversity/nature/environmental issues
 - **yellow if:**
 - Paper address issues of biodiversity/ecosystems AND discuss institutions/governance problems/barriers/unfitness AND discusses ways to overcome institutional/governance problems/barriers/unfitness
 - Paper conceptualizes drivers or patterns/types of institutional misfits RELATED TO biodiversity/nature/environmental issues AND discusses ways to overcome institutional/governance problems/barriers/unfitness
- **Screening Step #2: Full article reading and screening**
 - Papers are **excluded** when (i.e. marked as red):
 - Present model-based or simulation based results not based on real-life empirical results (quantitative or qualitative); these studies are not considered to warrant confidence since they do not rely on real-life evidence despite their value for policy, planning and governance
 - Analytical Questions:
 1. How is challenges/barriers/obstacles/blockages to transformative change described or conceptualised in this paper?
 2. How does this challenge is described –e.g. how it is produced (ways of thinking, doing, organising, relating and knowing)?
 - (2.1) How is biodiversity affected by this challenge (how is it described conceptually)?
 3. Does the paper present any case studies that can be used also in our chapter?
 - (3.1) What is the scale of the case study (regional, national, local/urban)?
 - (3.2) Where is the case study done (e.g. type of landscape)?
 - (3.3) Who are the main actors and institutions blocking transformative change?

(3.4) How are biodiversity and ecosystems affected by these challenges (empirically shown)?

(3.5) Are there any contradictions presented in the case studies?

4. What are the proposed or examined ways of overcoming the challenge(s)?